

TIJORAT BANKLARDA IQTISODIYOT XAVFSIZLIGINI TA'MINLASHDA KREDIT RISKNI KAMAYTIRISH

¹Xotamov Ibodulla Sa'dulloyevich, ²Tulkinova Maftuna Anvarbek qizi

¹I.f.d., professor

Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti

²Magistratura talabasi

Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11007929>

Annotatsiya. O'zbekiston tijorat banklarining moliyaviy faoliyatida kreditlar eng yuqori salmoqqa ega. Shu sababli, banklar kredit portfelining sifatini oshirishlari va kredit riskini kamaytirish usullarini takomillashtirishlari kerak. Maqolada tijorat banklarida kredit tavakkalchiligini kamaytirish yo'llari bilan bog'liq muammolar aniqlangan va ularni hal etishga qaratilgan ilmiy takliflar ishlab chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: kredit, kredit riski, likvidlik riski, bozor riski, foiz riski.

СНИЖЕНИЕ КРЕДИТНОГО РИСКА ПРИ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИИ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ В КОММЕРЧЕСКИХ БАНКАХ

Аннотация. Кредиты имеют наибольший вес в финансовой деятельности коммерческих банков Узбекистана. По этой причине банкам необходимо улучшить качество своего кредитного портфеля и усовершенствовать способы снижения кредитного риска. В статье рассмотрены пути снижения кредитного риска в коммерческих банках, выявлены проблемы и разработаны научные предложения, направленные на их решение.

Ключевые слова: кредит, кредитный риск, риск ликвидности, рыночный риск, процентный риск.

MITIGATION OF CREDIT RISK IN PROVIDING ECONOMIC SECURITY IN COMMERCIAL BANKS

Abstract. Loans have the highest weight in the financial activity of commercial banks of Uzbekistan. For this reason, banks need to improve the quality of their loan portfolio and improve ways to reduce credit risk. The article deals with ways to reduce credit risk in commercial banks problems are identified and scientific proposals aimed at solving them are developed.

Keywords: credit, credit risk, liquidity risk, market risk, interest rate risk.

INTRODUCTION

Loan portfolio and improving the quality of risk management, adhering to the moderate growth of lending volumes are defined as the priorities of reforming the republican banking system [1]. This, in turn, indicates that the issue of credit risk reduction is urgent.

In connection with this aspect, it is necessary to improve the lending process in the provision of economic security in the bank, to develop ways to eliminate and reduce the credit risks that arise in the lending process, and thereby to further increase the quality of the lending

process, to meet the needs of satisfaction, ensuring economic development and financial stability of the bank remains one of the main tasks.

Therefore, applying modern methods of credit risk reduction to the activities of commercial banks of our republic on a large scale and achieving credit efficiency based on this is one of the urgent issues in the banking sector today.

LITERATURE REVIEW

According to M. Matovnikov, "The main factor preventing the improvement of long-term lending practices of commercial banks is the lack of long-term resources in banks. A simple and realistic way to solve this problem is to take a loan from the Central Bank with the pledge of liquid assets" [2].

According to N. Sokolinskaya, careful monitoring of risks, formation of a quality credit portfolio, and having a good database for managing the lending process are the main aspects of ensuring the quality content of the loan [3].

According to I. Yudina's conclusion, the profitability of commercial banks' assets in developing countries directly depends on the level of credit risk, and as a result of the devaluation of the national currency, the inability of customers who received loans in foreign currency to repay the loan leads to an increase in the level of credit risk [4].

According to V. Usoskin, the bank's income from loans is directly related to risk management, and their loan portfolio is prone to all main types of risks: liquidity risk, interest risk, credit risk [5].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Comparison, grouping, logicity and historicity, analysis and synthesis, empirical and observational methods, experimental methods, archival research and other methods were effectively used as a research methodology.

Also, literature review and conceptual framework methods were used to collect and analyze theoretical concepts related to credit risks. In the literature review method, we have extensively reviewed the existing literature on credit risk, based on research papers, books, and reports from financial institutions and regulatory bodies.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The economic security of a bank represents the economic protection of its vital interests from unfair competition, the negative impact of external and internal threats and destabilizing factors.

One of the main tasks of the stable operation of a commercial bank is to ensure its economic security. It is based on preventing negative consequences on various aspects of the bank's economic security.

The main activity of a commercial bank involves risk. Today, in all banking systems, special attention is paid to the problem of improving risk management in the field of monetary relations. Measures to reduce such risks are one of the primary tasks of any commercial bank in order to increase the efficiency and liquidity of the bank and achieve maximum profit under given conditions. Among the wide variety of banking services, one of the most important types of their activities is credit operations. In the assets of commercial banks, loans occupy a strong position as the most voluminous and profitable items.

Credit transactions bring the highest income to the bank. Credit risk is the most significant component of banking threats, since most bank failures are caused by borrowers' non-repayment

of loans and the lack of a scientifically based strategy for managing credit risk. The population began to take out more loans, is in no hurry to pay off and thereby falls into credit bondage.

Credit risk is the probability of a financial loss resulting from a borrower's failure to repay a loan. Essentially, credit risk refers to the risk that a lender may not receive the owed principal and interest, which results in an interruption of cash flows and increased costs for collection [6]. Lenders can mitigate credit risk by analyzing factors about a borrower's creditworthiness, such as their current debt load and income.

Credit Risk Mitigation ("CRM") refers to the attempt by lenders, through the application of various safeguards or processes, to minimize the risk of losing all of their original investment (loans or debt) due to borrowers (companies or individuals) defaulting on their interest and principal payments. There can be a range of outcomes. Defaults can lead to significant revenue loss for lenders. There are strategies to mitigate credit risk such as risk-based pricing, inserting covenants, post-disbursement monitoring, and limiting sectoral exposure.

For banks and other types of lending institutions, having robust CRM is pivotal to avoiding a surge in defaults and non-performing assets (NPA), which can very adversely impact their financial performance or even result in insolvency.

As stated above, there are certain credit risk mitigation strategies, i.e. risk control strategies that banks and other lending institutions deploy to mitigate the probability that borrowers will default on their loans, and to reduce the number of non-performing assets. An outline of each strategy is given below:

5 Cs of credit: these provide lenders a framework for credit risk mitigation and help in identifying the inherent risk in a loan. The 5 Cs of credit are character, capacity, capital, collateral, and conditions (purpose of the loan, cost, and tenure).

Figure 1. The 5 Cs of credit.

Initial risk assessment: the credit team performs [credit analysis](#) of a company that wants to borrow. This involves assessing business risk and financial risk.

Structuring of loan: the point of structuring a loan is to mitigate risk. It includes details such as to whom the bank is lending, if there are any complexities in the borrower's corporate structure, choosing the right kind of loan that matches the future cash flows of the borrower with the repayment schedule, etc.

Credit memo: includes details such as [debt capacity](#) of the borrower, clarity on risks involved, and mitigating factors to those risks.

Loan syndication: in the case of a larger loan, the lender may seek to mitigate credit risk by going in for loan syndication, which involves selling down the bank's exposure to the loan to a bank group.

Loan protection: involves the issue of seniority of debt and legal contractual ranking of creditors. Further, the lender takes into account the securities, guarantees, and collateral that a borrower can give.

Pricing of loan: which is encapsulated by risk versus return and is also driven by supply and demand.

Risk-based pricing: in this type of pricing, banks charge different rates of interest to borrowers with different risk profiles. In other words, higher (lower) interest is charged to those borrowers where the chances of default are higher (lower).

Lending institutions attempt to gauge the risk appetite of different borrowers and their respective ability to fully service the loan and accordingly charge them a higher or a lower rate of interest. In attempting to gauge the above, lending institutions analyze how robust or weak is the financial condition of the borrower and/or their past record of servicing debt.

Debt Covenants: Lending institutions often insert loan [covenants](#), which include financial, technical, business level, and operational covenants) into the loan agreements. Such covenants are agreements that stipulate the terms and conditions of loan policies between the borrower and the lending institution before funds are disbursed to the borrower. Here, the lender puts a number of restrictions in place that a borrower agrees to, which are meant to protect the lender from the risks associated with the loan.

For example, if a company is taking out a loan, in order to expand its operations, the bank may ask it to sign a covenant that states the minimum amount of revenue generated by the company that must be reinvested. The underlying intention is to ensure that the company remains profitable so that the ability to repay the loan is not jeopardized. Usually, loan covenants include the maximum debt-to-equity ratios that a company must adhere to.

Post Disbursement Monitoring: lending institutions need to ensure that the borrowers make proper use of the loan that is disbursed to them and they have the adequate cash flow to service their loan on time. Therefore, they may demand of the borrower to furnish them with their financial statements – balance sheet, income statement, and cash flow statements – in a predefined format either every month, quarterly, or annually. This helps them to assess the cash flow of the borrowing company and whether it will be able to easily service the debt or not.

Exposure limits: an important element of credit [risk management](#) is the establishment of exposure limits across sectors, to minimize the chances of default and keep non-performing assets at a prudent level. In certain industry sectors, the probability of default is higher than in others, Consequently, lenders may decide to lend less to those sectors where the risk of credit default is higher. For example, the real estate and pharmaceutical sectors are often considered high risk sectors vis-à-vis credit risk.

Collateral: the most common type of credit risk mitigation technique. It refers to the pledging or hypothecating by a borrower to a bank or lending institution. Collateral is used as an item of value to obtain a loan and minimizes risks for lenders. For example, if a borrowing company is unable to service the debt or repay as its cash flows are not adequate, then the lending institution can seize or take control of the collateral that is pledged and sell it to reduce or recoup the loss. The most common type of collateralized loans are mortgages and car loans.

Figure 2. Best practices for credit risk mitigation in banks.

Banks and other types of lending institutions attempt to maintain credit risk exposure within prudent and acceptable parameters, which is the objective of credit risk mitigation within such organizations. CRM enables lending institutions to manage their cash flows more efficiently, lowers non-performing assets, enhances customer management and improves their bottom line (profits).

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

We recommend the following conclusions and proposals to reduce the credit risk of loans issued by commercial banks:

- Comprehensive approach to the received application for credit, i.e. correct and perfect implementation of initial monitoring. In particular, it is necessary to pay attention to the client's worldview, his social situation, his position among business partners, and his experience in this field, and during this period, ensure the completeness of the set of documents he submits to the bank, and check their accuracy. .

- His financial situation should be thoroughly analyzed and objectively evaluated by the employee of the credit department;

- Continuous monitoring of the client's work according to the business plan, the circulation of funds in the account, the settlement with the suppliers of goods in due time, the acceptance of overdue receivables and payables take measures not to eat;

- Constantly monitoring the conditions of maintenance and operation of property provided as credit security;

- If a third-party guaranty contract is provided as credit security, it is necessary to analyze the financial statements of the guarantor once a quarter and study its solvency together with the client. In this process, the responsibility of the credit department is important. Indifference to the risks shown in our research prevents credit risks.

List of used literature:

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5992 of May 12, 2020 "On the strategy of reforming the banking system of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2025"
2. Matovnikov M. Yu. The Russian banking system and long-term resources//Money and Credit. – Moscow, 2013. – No. 5. – P. 19.
3. Sokolinskaya N. E. Problems of credit portfolio management in modern conditions // Banking. – Moscow, 1999. - No. 9. – pp. 18–19.
4. Yudina I. N. Banking system in developing economies: experience of formation, development and crises. Monograph. – M.: INFRA-M, 2013. – P. 230–231.
5. Usoskin V. M. Modern commercial bank: management and operations. – M.:LENAND, 2019. – P. 218.
6. Mian A., Rao K., Sufi A. Household Balance Sheets, Consumption, and the Economic Slump//Quarterly Journal of
7. Economics. – 2013.
8. Abdullaeva Sh.Z. Credit and lending practices. T.: "ECONOMY-FINANCE". 2017.
9. Dawane, Sudarshan, Kishanrao. (2023). Risk Management in Public and Private Sector Banks. International Journal of Advanced Research in Science, Communication and Technology, Available from: 10.48175/ijarsct-8146
10. www.cbu.uz